

OMISSION OF SENTINEL LYMPH NODE BIOPSY IN EARLY BREAST CANCER: A CRITICAL APPRAISAL OF THE SOUND, INSEMA, AND BOOG 2013-08 TRIALS WITH A PROPOSED CLINICAL SELECTION ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT Should sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) be omitted in carefully selected patients with clinically node-negative (cN0) early breast cancer? This question has become central in contemporary surgical oncology. For selected postmenopausal women with cT1, HR-positive/HER2-negative tumours undergoing breast-conserving therapy, recent phase III randomized trials suggest that omission of SLNB may provide outcomes comparable to standard axillary staging. Axillary management has evolved from routine axillary lymph node dissection to selective SLNB. Recent randomized trials—including SOUND and INSEMA, with emerging phase III data from BOOG 2013-08—have evaluated the safety of omitting SLNB in patients with negative preoperative axillary ultrasound. This review critically appraises these trials, focusing on their non-inferiority design, endpoint selection, imaging-based staging, biological selection, radiotherapy considerations, and implications for adjuvant therapy decisions. Despite differing primary endpoints, SOUND and INSEMA demonstrated statistical non-inferiority of SLNB omission in strictly selected populations, predominantly characterized by small HR-positive/HER2-negative tumours and negative axillary imaging. However, premenopausal patients, HER2-positive and triple-negative subtypes, cT2 tumours, and invasive lobular carcinoma were underrepresented, and evidence for these groups remains limited. Based on available randomized evidence, key features supporting safe omission include postmenopausal status, cT1 tumour size (≤ 2 cm), HR-positive/HER2-negative biology, negative axillary ultrasound, planned breast-conserving surgery, and whole-breast irradiation. SLNB omission should therefore be considered only for carefully selected patients within a multidisciplinary framework rather than adopted as routine practice. Longer follow-up and further subgroup validation remain necessary to confirm long-term safety.

KEYWORDS Sentinel lymph node biopsy, Axillary staging, Early breast cancer, Surgical de-escalation, Non-inferiority trials, SOUND trial, INSEMA trial, Axillary ultrasound

Introduction

Over the past three decades, major developments have transformed axillary staging techniques for early-stage breast cancer. Previously, clinicians regarded axillary lymph node dissection (ALND) as essential for locoregional disease control and prognostic assessment, but sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) has largely replaced it.[1,2] Historical evidence shows ALND causes up to 30–40% lymphedema, driving the search for safer staging methods.[3] Randomised clinical trials (e.g., NSABP

B-32) demonstrated that SLNB delivers equivalent oncologic outcomes to ALND while greatly reducing treatment-related morbidity.[4,5] Consequently, clinicians now use SLNB as the standard axillary staging method for patients with clinically node-negative (cN0) breast cancer, providing accurate pathological evaluation with a notably lower incidence of adverse effects, including lymphedema, persistent pain, sensory disturbances, and limited shoulder mobility.[6] Notably, SLNB results in lymphedema rates of about 3–5%, compared with 19–30% after ALND.[7]

Progress in systemic therapies, radiotherapy techniques, and molecular profiling has further changed how axillary nodal status influences breast cancer management. Current adjuvant treatment strategies progressively depend on tumour biology, molecular subtype, and genomic analysis instead than only nodal involvement.[8,9] Pivotal randomised trials demonstrate that, for selected patients with limited sentinel node involvement who undergo breast-conserving surgery and receive appropriate systemic therapy, completion of ALND does not improve long-term survival.[1,9,10] These results uphold the oncologic safety of axillary surgical de-escalation in carefully selected node-positive patients and encourage a move toward individualised, selective axillary staging.

In this developing landscape, researchers now focus on whether patients with early-stage clinically node-negative breast cancer require SLNB. When axillary pathological findings do not notably affect systemic therapy or radiotherapy planning for biologically favourable tumours, and adjuvant treatments achieve regional disease control, omitting axillary surgery could further reduce treatment-related morbidity.[11-13]

A former hypothetical question is now a practical one. More surgeons are caring for patients whose nodal status won't affect adjuvant choices, but SLNB still carries risks.[1,12] This switch from anatomic to biological decision-making draws attention to the need for clear, evidence-based criteria for safely skipping axillary surgery.

Three recent randomised controlled trials—SOUND, INSEMA, and BOOG 2013-08—comprehensively examined the oncologic safety of omitting sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) among patients eligible for breast-conserving surgery who had negative clinical axillary findings and underwent standardised preoperative axillary ultrasound.[11-13] Although all three studies employed a non-inferiority design, each used different eligibility criteria, primary endpoints, imaging methodologies, and statistical approaches. [11-13] These methodical differences entail careful interpretation and detailed consideration when clinicians apply the findings to practice.

This article appraises the methods of the SOUND, INSEMA, and BOOG 2013-08 trials, defines the scope of their applicability scope, and proposes a pragmatic, evidence-based framework to guide multidisciplinary decisions on SLNB omission in early breast cancer.

Overview of Contemporary Randomised Trials

SOUND Trial

The Sentinel Node vs Observation After Axillary Ultrasound (SOUND) trial is a prospective, multicenter, phase III randomised study conducted within a non-inferiority framework across multiple European institutions. [11] The trial enrolled women of any age with invasive breast cancer measuring ≤ 2 cm (cT1), clinically node-negative (cN0) axillae, and negative preop-

erative axillary ultrasound findings. [11] Participants were randomised in a 1:1 ratio to either undergo a sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) or not undergo axillary surgical staging.[11]

The primary endpoint of the study was 5-year distant disease-free survival (DDFS). [11] Among the intention-to-treat population of 1,405 patients, the 5-year DDFS was 97.7% in the SLNB group and 98.0% in the observation group (hazard ratio 0.84; 90% confidence interval [CI], 0.45–1.54), meeting the predetermined criteria for non-inferiority. The median follow-up was 5.7 years.[11]

The tumour characteristics in the study population were predominantly biologically favourable. [11] Hormone receptor-positive/HER2-negative tumours accounted for 87.8% of cases, and 13.7% of patients who underwent SLNB had pathological nodal involvement. [11] This evidence shows a cohort with a low baseline nodal burden and limited biological heterogeneity. In this highly selected population, omitting SLNB did not compromise systemic disease control during short- to intermediate-term follow-up.[11]

INSEMA Trial

The INSEMA (Intergroup-Sentinel-Mamma) trial is a large, phase III randomised non-inferiority study designed to determine whether sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) can be safely omitted in patients with clinically node-negative (cN0) early breast cancer undergoing breast-conserving surgery.[12] The trial enrolled > 5,000 patients from multiple European centres.[12]

The primary outcome measure was invasive disease-free survival (iDFS), assessed in the per-protocol population. [12] After a median follow-up of 73.6 months, the 5-year iDFS was 91.9% in the omission group and 91.7% in the SLNB group (hazard ratio [HR], 0.91; 95% confidence interval [CI], 0.73–1.14). [12] These results remained within the predefined non-inferiority margin, with the upper limit of the hazard ratio set at 1.271. [12]

Regional failure events remained rare in both treatment arms. The omission group had axillary recurrence in 1.0% of patients, and the SLNB group in 0.3%, showing a low overall burden of regional events. Patient-reported outcomes showed clinically meaningful benefits when patients omitted axillary surgery. The omission group experienced lymphedema in 1.8% of cases, less than the SLNB group's 5.7%, confirming reduced treatment-related morbidity.[12]

Similar to the SOUND trial, the INSEMA cohort was defined by favourable tumour biology. Approximately 90% of the patients were aged ≥ 50 years, and hormone receptor-positive/HER2-negative tumours comprised approximately 95% of the cases. Only 9.6% of the patients had cT2 disease, and grade 3 tumours were uncommon. [11,12] These characteristics indicate that the demonstration of non-inferiority primarily reflects outcomes in a carefully selected, low-risk population.

BOOG 2013-08 Trial

The BOOG 2013-08 trial, a Dutch prospective, multicenter, phase III randomised study, used a non-inferiority design to assess whether clinicians can safely omit sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) in clinically node-negative patients undergoing breast-conserving therapy.[13] Eligible participants presented with unilateral invasive breast cancer staged as cT1–2 and produced negative findings on preoperative axillary ultrasound. Investigators

required cytological or histological confirmation for suspicious lymph nodes before enrollment.[13]

The primary endpoint of the trial was regional recurrence at 5 years. [13] Secondary outcomes included distant disease-free survival (DDFS), overall survival (OS), axillary morbidity, quality of life, and cost-benefit analysis. [13] Interim analyses at 5 years, presented publicly, demonstrated low regional recurrence rates in both study arms. [13] The absolute differences observed to date remained within the predefined non-inferiority margin of 5%. [13] No statistically significant differences in the DDFS were observed at the time of interim reporting.[13]

Nevertheless, mature oncological results have not yet been fully published in a peer-reviewed format. Therefore, BOOG 2013-08 should currently be viewed as providing supportive phase III evidence, with definitive conclusions dependent on the availability of complete long-term outcome data.

A key methodological aspect of the BOOG trial is its strict reliance on standardised, quality-controlled axillary ultrasound for patient selection. In effect, the study directly tested an imaging-driven strategy for omitting axillary surgery in patients undergoing breast-conserving treatment combined with radiotherapy.

Current Clinical Trials

In addition to SOUND, INSEMA, and BOOG 2013-08, multiple ongoing trials are investigating imaging-based approaches to avoid axillary surgery in clinically node-negative patients. The NAUTILUS study [14] represents this research direction. Although outcome data are unavailable, the sustained progress of these trials emphasises persistent international interest in establishing criteria for safe axillary de-escalation.

Comparative Study of Trial Designs

SOUND, INSEMA, and BOOG 2013-08 are all randomised non-inferiority trials that enrolled patients with clinically node-negative breast cancer who underwent breast-conserving surgery.[11-13] Despite this shared conceptual framework, these studies vary considerably in methodological aspects, such as primary endpoints, tumour size eligibility, statistical non-inferiority margins, imaging procedures, and the maturity of follow-up data. SOUND assessed systemic safety, INSEMA assessed total invasive events, and BOOG assessed regional control. [11-13]

The SOUND trial prioritised distant disease-free survival and enrolled only patients with cT1 tumours.[11] In contrast, the INSEMA trial used invasive disease-free survival as its primary endpoint and included a more extensive patient population. [12,15] The BOOG trial, in contrast, selected regional recurrence as its principal outcome and emphasised stringent imaging-based selection. [13] Such distinctions themselves demonstrate different clinical priorities: systemic disease control, overall invasive recurrence risk, and regional control, rather than methodological variation alone.

As mature, peer-reviewed oncologic results from BOOG 2013-08 are not yet available, direct comparisons among these trials should be treated with caution. [13] Applying this evidence to clinical practice calls for close scrutiny of factors, including biological patient selection, the quality and standardisation of axillary imaging, radiotherapy techniques, and follow-up duration.

Critical Methodological Appraisal

Non-inferiority Design and Endpoint Selection

SOUND, INSEMA, and BOOG 2013-08 were all designed as randomised non-inferiority trials. However, these studies differ in several major methodological aspects, such as the selection of primary endpoints, statistical margins, and the conceptual focus of outcome assessment.[11-13]

The BOOG 2013-08 trial defined 5-year regional recurrence as its primary endpoint, focusing directly on the oncologic safety of omitting axillary surgery. [13] This endpoint selection corresponds to the primary clinical concern of SLNB omission: whether regional disease control can be maintained without surgical staging. However, regional recurrence events in early-stage breast cancer are rare. In such low-event settings, small absolute differences may appear proportionally large, and confidence intervals tend to be wide. Consequently, fineness in estimating the predefined non-inferiority margin is inherently limited. The BOOG adopted a 5% absolute margin; therefore, interpreting the results entails careful assessment of both the number of observed events and the statistical limits of the analysis.

In contrast, the SOUND trial selected 5-year distant disease-free survival (DDFS) as its primary endpoint. The surrogate validity of DDFS relative to OS has been supported in pooled analyses of adjuvant trials. [11,18] This broader outcome emphasises systemic oncologic safety rather than regional disease control. The non-inferiority margin in SOUND was set at 2.5%, representing a more conservative threshold than that used in BOOG, and the analysis used a 90% confidence interval, which is standard in oncology non-inferiority trials. Because DDFS includes distant events that are not directly attributable to axillary management, the isolated contribution of surgical staging to the primary endpoint becomes less discernible.

The INSEMA trial employed invasive disease-free survival (iDFS) as the primary endpoint. Both iDFS and invasive breast cancer-free survival (IBCFS) have demonstrated strong trial-level correlation with overall survival in adjuvant chemotherapy trials.[19] This composite measure encompasses locoregional recurrence, distant recurrence, and contralateral invasive breast cancer. Although this broader endpoint increases the number of events and enhances statistical power in large study populations, it reduces the specificity of the analysis regarding axillary recurrence.[16]

Collectively, the three trials address related yet distinct clinical questions.

- The SOUND trial prioritises systemic oncological safety.[11]
- The INSEMA trial evaluated overall invasive disease control.[12]
- The BOOG trial focused on regional control within the axilla.[13]

Because these endpoints capture different aspects of oncologic outcomes, direct comparisons across trials require a detailed review.[16,17]

Notably, none of these studies was designed to demonstrate equivalence among treatment strategies. The main goal was to exclude clinically unacceptable inferiority within prespecified statistical margins. Consequently, a lack of statistical significance does not indicate that the approaches provide identical outcomes. Rather, the evidence suggests that omitting the SLNB did not exceed the predefined inferiority threshold under the conditions studied.[17]

Feature	SOUND	INSEMA	BOOG 2013-08
Design	Phase III RCT	Phase III RCT	Phase III RCT
N	1,405	>5,000	1,733
Tumor size	≤ 2 cm	cT1–2	cT1–2
Primary endpoint	5-year DDFS	iDFS	Regional recurrence
Non-inferiority margin	2.5% absolute	HR 1.271	5% absolute
Median follow-up	5.7 years	~6 years	~5 years (interim)
HR+ /HER2- proportion	87.8%	>90%	Predominant
Imaging requirement	Mandatory US	Clinical ± US	Mandatory US

Table 1 Summary of the the principal design characteristics and primary outcomes of SOUND, INSEMA, and BOOG 2013-08.

Implications of Lower-than-Expected Event Rates for Statistical Power

All trials evaluating the omission of axillary surgery were designed based on anticipated event rates that were higher than those observed during the follow-up. [20]

In the INSEMA trial, the sample size calculations assumed 851 invasive disease-free survival (iDFS) events during the study period.[12] However, the planned number of events was not achieved, warranting a time-driven approach for the primary analysis. A comparable pattern of lower-than-expected event incidence was also observed in the SOUND trial and in the interim analyses of BOOG 2013-08.[11,13]

In non-inferiority trial designs, a reduction in event frequency directly decreases the total number of outcome events available for analysis. When fewer events accrue than anticipated, the effective statistical power decreases, resulting in wider confidence intervals and reduced precision, particularly in subgroup analyses.[21]

Even with these limitations, the upper bounds of the confidence intervals reported in both SOUND and INSEMA remained below their respective non-inferiority margins, thereby meeting the predefined statistical criteria.[11,12] For instance, in the SOUND trial, the 90% confidence interval for the hazard ratio of distant disease-free survival extended up to 1.54, while the non-inferiority boundary was 1.80.[11] In INSEMA, the upper bound of the 95% confidence interval for the hazard ratio for invasive disease-free survival was 1.14, with a non-inferiority margin of 1.271.[12] This means that although non-inferiority was achieved, the confidence intervals were relatively wide, reflecting residual uncertainty about the absolute risk difference. The low number of observed events limited the interpretive granularity for rare outcomes or subgroup effects. Subgroup analyses, notably those involving biologically aggressive tumours or less frequently represented clinical scenarios, are especially susceptible to Type II error under these conditions.[22]

Current evidence confirms that omitting sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) is non-inferior in the studied populations. However, these data do not establish absolute equivalence and do not eliminate uncertainty in higher-risk subgroups.

Reliance on Imaging and Reproducibility in Axillary Assessment

The omission of sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) is dependent on the accuracy as well as reliability of preoperative axillary imaging.

Both the SOUND and BOOG 2013-08 trials required negative axillary ultrasound examinations prior to enrollment, with suspicious lymph nodes undergoing tissue sampling.[11,13,23] This imaging-based selection approach is likely to reduce the

baseline prevalence of nodal disease. In the SOUND trial, pathological nodal involvement was identified in 13.7% of patients who underwent SLNB, indicating that the imaging criteria effectively excluded individuals with a higher probability of axillary metastases [11].

To maintain reproducibility, axillary ultrasound should be performed using standardised, quality-controlled protocols. Critical aspects of a strong imaging assessment include the following [23]:

- Interpretation by specialised breast radiologists
- Systematic evaluation of lymph node morphology
- In the BOOG 2013-08 protocol, cortical thickening > 2.3 mm was defined as the threshold for performing fine-needle aspiration biopsy, in accordance with Dutch breast cancer guidelines. However, comparable millimetre-specific thresholds were not uniformly protocol-mandated across all omission trials[13].
- Preservation of the fatty hilum within lymph nodes
- Absence of focal cortical bulging or eccentric cortical thickening
- Lack of rounded lymph node morphology
- Image-guided biopsy of any lymph nodes deemed suspicious

The INSEMA trial enrolled clinically node-negative patients across a large multicenter network.[12] Although this approach elevates generalizability, it may cause variability in imaging practices across institutions. Whether the diagnostic performance detected in the controlled environment of a clinical trial can be consistently replicated in routine clinical settings is a key element in expanded implementation.

Certain tumour histologies present additional diagnostic difficulties. For example, invasive lobular carcinoma exhibits a diffuse infiltrative growth pattern that can reduce ultrasound sensitivity relative to invasive ductal carcinoma. In these cases, exclusive reliance on imaging may increase the risk of axillary understaging.[23]

Therefore, strategies for surgical de-escalation must incorporate rigorous imaging standards and multidisciplinary quality assurance systems to guarantee patient safety and reproducibility. Institutions considering omission strategies should formally audit axillary ultrasound performance, including annual documentation of false-negative rates. To facilitate pragmatic implementation, a simple audit process can be followed: (1) collect and review a sample of consecutive cases with both preoperative axillary ultrasound and corresponding surgical pathology (e.g., 20-30 cases per year, or as feasible for the institution's volume); (2) calculate negative predictive value, sensitivity, and specificity for axillary ultrasound in detecting nodal metastases; (3) record and periodically report the results through multidisciplinary

team meetings; and (4) manage any differences or patterns suggestive of underperformance with targeted retraining or standardisation. As a practical benchmark, institutions implementing SLNB omission strategies may aim for axillary ultrasound performance associated with a negative predictive value of approximately $\geq 95\%$ in clinically node-negative patients. This corresponds to a post-test probability of occult nodal disease below roughly 5% in the highly selected populations studied in omission trials. This threshold does not derive directly from the statistical non-inferiority margins used in SOUND, INSEMA, or BOOG 2013-08, as these trials did not specify an acceptable imaging false-negative rate. Rather, it represents an expert-informed quality-assurance benchmark intended to ensure that the diagnostic performance of axillary imaging approximates that achieved in the controlled environment of randomised trials. Centres considering omitting SLNB are encouraged to audit the accuracy of their axillary ultrasound assessment before adopting omission strategies, using these benchmarks to gauge their capability to implement them.[23]

Biological Selection and Representation of Subgroups

The three randomised trials predominantly enrolled patients with biologically favourable disease profiles. In the SOUND trial, hormone receptor-positive/human epidermal growth factor receptor 2-negative (HR+/HER2-) tumours accounted for 87.8% of cases.[11] The INSEMA trial demonstrated a similar distribution, with most patients presenting with HR+/HER2- disease, whereas triple-negative and HER2-positive subtypes were minimally represented.[12] As these molecular subtypes are typically associated with lower early recurrence risk, their predominance in the study cohorts likely contributed to the low baseline event rates observed.[24]

Epidemiologic data from population-based analyses contextualise these results. For tumours classified as T1c-T2 with triple-negative or HER2-positive biology, nodal involvement rates range from 30% to 50%, which is substantially higher than in HR+/HER2- disease.[25-27] Therefore, applying SLNB omission strategies to biologically aggressive subtypes is not currently supported by stratified non-inferiority evidence from these trials.

Tumour Size Considerations

The strength of the evidence supporting omitting SLNB varies with tumour size.

Level I (Strong Evidence)

cT1 tumours (≤ 2 cm): This group was directly evaluated in the SOUND trial using a conservative non-inferiority design with a systemic endpoint. Consequently, the available data provided the most reliable validation for omission within this tumour size category.[11,24]

Level II (Limited Evidence)

cT2 tumours (2–5 cm): Representation was limited in the randomised evidence. In the INSEMA cohort, approximately 9.6% of enrolled patients had cT2 disease. Subgroup analyses for this category were therefore statistically underpowered. Importantly, the available analyses did not display a consistent point estimate suggesting harm from SLNB omission; rather, the confidence intervals were wide due to the small number of patients and

events. Consequently, the current evidence for cT2 tumours should be interpreted as limited by statistical exactness rather than indicating an adverse oncologic signal.[12,24]

Level III (Hypothesis-Generating)

Therefore, omitting SLNB in cT2 disease should be considered hypothesis-generating rather than confirmatory. More clarification will be provided once mature subgroup analyses from BOOG 2013-08 are available.[13, 25, 27, 28]

Histological Grade Considerations

High-grade tumours were infrequently represented in the omission trials. Grade 3 lesions were underrepresented, and none of the studies was adequately powered to establish non-inferiority within this subgroup. Although current data do not demonstrate an increased risk of regional recurrence among patients with higher-grade disease, the limited number of events raises the possibility of a Type II error and increases statistical ambiguity. The absence of evidence is not evidence of absence; therefore, recommendations for caution reflect insufficient validation rather than confirmed inferiority.[12,24]

The histological grade should not be interpreted in isolation. Grade 2 tumours represent a biologically heterogeneous category, and high proliferative activity (e.g., elevated Ki-67 consistent with a luminal B phenotype) may confer a greater risk of nodal involvement and therapeutic implications. Randomised omission trials did not stratify by proliferation markers. Accordingly, the interpretation of “low to intermediate grade” should be contextualised within a more extensive biological risk assessment rather than applied as an isolated criterion.[29]

Neoadjuvant Considerations

Randomised trials assessing the omission of sentinel lymph node biopsy were performed in the context of primary surgery (neoadjuvant cohorts were excluded from all three trials). Therefore, these data are not directly applicable to patients receiving neoadjuvant systemic therapy.[11-13]

Omitting axillary staging may theoretically influence the selection between neoadjuvant and adjuvant systemic therapy in a small subset of patients with occult nodal disease. However, for small hormone receptor-positive/HER2-negative tumours, the decision to use neoadjuvant chemotherapy is primarily based on tumour biology rather than nodal status.[30] In contrast, neoadjuvant therapy is generally recommended for HER2-positive and triple-negative breast cancers, regardless of axillary staging. Because randomised omission trials excluded patients who received neoadjuvant therapy, the safety of omitting the sentinel lymph node biopsy in this context remains unknown. Evidence supporting omission after neoadjuvant chemotherapy, especially in biologically aggressive subtypes, is investigational and currently limited to emerging data [30-32]. Therefore, multidisciplinary evaluation is essential when considering neoadjuvant therapy.

Impact on Adjuvant Treatment Decisions

The central argument for omitting sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) is the growing importance of nodal status in guiding systemic therapy decisions.

In hormone receptor-positive/HER2-negative (HR+/HER2-) breast cancer, treatment decisions are more frequently incorporating genomic classifiers and tumour biology, in addition

to factors other than solely nodal burden. Analyses from real-world medical records indicate that only 7%–14% of patients with cN0 T1 HR+/HER2– tumours would have a change in systemic therapy based exclusively on nodal findings [24]. These data suggest that, for many patients, axillary pathological staging may not substantially influence adjuvant treatment recommendations.[33]

Genomic Assays and the Nx Classification

Most genomic assays currently implemented in clinical practice, such as Oncotype DX and MammaPrint, have undergone prospective validation in cohorts stratified by pathological nodal status (N0 versus N1–3). When sentinel lymph node biopsy is omitted, patients are classified as having pathological Nx, a category not explicitly included in the original set validation studies for these assays.

Although the SOUND and INSEMA trials reported no significant increase in chemotherapy utilisation in the omission arms, stable treatment rates do not fully address the potential risk of under-treatment.[34] Specifically, if occult nodal micrometastases are present but remain undetected owing to the omission of sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB), genomic risk interpretation may default to a clinically node-negative (cN0) framework.[34] This scenario could alter risk calibration in borderline cases, particularly among premenopausal patients, in whom nodal status influences chemotherapy benefit in trials such as RxPONDER.[24]

It is important to note that patients enrolled in omission trials were highly selected, with negative high-quality axillary imaging and low baseline nodal event rates. Therefore, the absolute probability of clinically meaningful occult nodal burden is likely to be small within this population. However, the performance characteristics and predictive calibration of genomic assays in patients with pathological Nx have not been prospectively validated. Consequently, omitting SLNB results in a residual area of biological uncertainty, particularly in younger patients or in genomic intermediate-risk categories, in which nodal information may influence therapeutic decision-making.[24,34]

In clinical practice, clinicians faced with an Nx result after omitting SLNB should approach genomic assay interpretation with greater caution. Adjuvant therapy decisions should be informed by the totality of clinical, pathological, and imaging data rather than reliance on assay results alone. When applying a genomic signature to an Nx patient, it is advisable to:

- Clearly document the rationale for SLNB omission and Nx classification in the medical record.
- Interpret genomic assay scores in the context of negative high-quality axillary imaging and the patient's baseline clinical risk.
- Recognise that published assay risk thresholds and benefit estimates were established in cohorts with known nodal status.
- Where uncertainty exists, particularly in premenopausal or intermediate-risk patients, discuss the limitations of current evidence directly with the patient. Engage the multidisciplinary team to consider additional clinicopathological features, patient preference, and, if necessary, consider closer follow-up as well as the involvement of genomic tumour boards.

Shared decision-making ought to maintain a strong patient-focused approach through explicit communication both the expected reduction in surgical morbidity and the small, as yet unquantified, risk of occult nodal disease that could influence therapeutic decisions. Engaging patients in an open discussion about these considerations enables them to weigh individual values and preferences in light of the limited prospective evidence available for the Nx subgroup, thus facilitating truly informed and patient-tailored choices.

The very low regional recurrence rates seen across omission trials should be interpreted within the broader structure of multimodal therapy. A substantial proportion of patients received effective adjuvant systemic treatment, including endocrine therapy, chemotherapy, and HER2-targeted agents, as indicated. These therapies, when used independently, reduce the risk of distant and locoregional recurrence. When combined with whole-breast irradiation, which frequently delivers a partial dose to level I and portions of level II axillary nodes, the resulting regional control reflects the cumulative effect of biological selection, systemic therapy, and radiotherapy rather than surgical omission alone. [12,24,34] Accordingly, axillary de-escalation represents a redistribution of regional management within a coordinated multimodal strategy rather than a withdrawal of regional therapy.

Radiotherapy Technique and Incidental Axillary Coverage

The oncologic safety of omitting SLNB in contemporary randomised trials was established in the context of conventional whole-breast irradiation delivered with standard tangential fields. Although axillary treatment was not protocol-mandated, these earlier techniques regularly delivered substantial radiation doses to level I and portions of level II axillary nodes.[35]

In modern radiotherapy practice, highly conformal techniques, such as intensity-modulated radiotherapy (IMRT), volumetric-modulated arc therapy (VMAT), and proton therapy, may significantly reduce unintended axillary exposure when treatment plans are optimised to spare adjacent normal tissues. Under these conditions, reliance on an uncontrolled “incidental” dose cannot be assumed to reproduce the biological environment in which non-inferiority was demonstrated.[36,37]

The relative contribution of incidental axillary irradiation versus the intrinsically low nodal burden of the selected trial populations is still unclear. The very low rates of regional recurrence observed in SOUND and INSEMA may therefore reflect both biological patient selection and the effects of multimodal therapy instead of a direct radiobiological effect of incidental nodal dose alone.

Accordingly, when SLNB is omitted, awareness of the historical treatment context is important. Conventional tangential whole-breast radiotherapy fields used in the randomised trials typically delivered partial dose exposure to level I and portions of level II axillary nodes. In centres employing highly conformal techniques such as IMRT or VMAT, treatment planning should therefore acknowledge that axillary exposure may differ from that in the trial environment. To support safe omission of SLNB when using modern radiotherapy, clinicians should review treatment plans dosimetrically to confirm adequate incidental axillary coverage. Important steps comprise verifying that level I and at least part of level II axillary nodes receive a meaningful portion of the prescribed breast dose—typically a mean dose of 60–70% with substantial volume receiving at

least 90–95% of the prescription dose (for example, V90–95%). This may require including axillary levels I–II as structures in the planning system and reviewing the dose-volume histogram (DVH) for these lymphatic regions. If using IMRT, VMAT, or other highly conformal modalities, the treatment team should carefully check that beam arrangements do not completely exclude the lower axilla unless specifically intended. However, routine intentional irradiation of the lower axilla cannot currently be considered evidence-based and should not be regarded as a mandatory component of SLNB omission strategies.[36,38] Unverified incidental irradiation should not be considered sufficient assurance of regional control in the era of contemporary conformal radiotherapy.

Potential Compensatory Treatment Escalation

Another methodological concern is that omitting axillary surgery could indirectly result in increased use of systemic therapy. In the SOUND trial, chemotherapy was administered to 20.1% of patients in the SLNB arm and 17.5% in the omission arm, providing no evidence of compensatory escalation when nodal staging was omitted. Radiotherapy patterns were comparable between the groups.[11,39]

Similarly, the INSEMA trial did not report significant differences in systemic therapy utilisation between treatment arms, although in-depth analyses of treatment redistribution were not a primary study objective. [12] Comprehensive peer-reviewed data on systemic treatment distribution are still pending for BOOG 2013-08.

To summarize, current evidence does not display systematic escalation of systemic therapy when SLNB is omitted. [33] However, comprehensive analyses of treatment redistribution remain limited.

Duration of Follow-up, Late Recurrence Risk, and Implications of Regional Relapse

The duration of follow-up is a main limitation of the current evidence base. In the SOUND trial, the median follow-up was 5.7 years [11]. Because the majority of enrolled patients had hormone receptor-positive disease, this interval captures the dynamics of early recurrence.[6,30,40] Large-scale meta-analyses by the Early Breast Cancer Trialists' Collaborative Group have demonstrated that in estrogen receptor-positive breast cancer, the risk of distant recurrence persists steadily between 5 and 20 years after diagnosis. Among women with node-negative ER-positive tumours, the cumulative risk of distant recurrence between years 5 and 20 is approximately 10%, which substantially increases in the node-positive population.[41]

Accordingly, follow-up periods of 5–6 years may underestimate the total long-term risk profile in biologically favourable subtypes characterised by delayed relapse patterns. Although non-inferiority has been demonstrated for early- and intermediate-term outcomes, durable long-term equivalence, especially with regard to late distant metastasis, is still unproven.[11,40,42]

An additional consideration is the management of regional recurrence. Although axillary recurrence rates in omission trials were very low (approximately 1% or less at 5 years), salvage treatment in such cases typically consists of axillary lymph node dissection (ALND), often combined with regional radiotherapy if not previously administered. [10,11,30,40] Thus, omission of

the SLNB does not eliminate the possibility of more extensive axillary surgery but may defer it to a small subset of patients who develop regional relapse. From a population perspective, this represents a redistribution rather than a complete avoidance of surgical morbidity. However, given the very low absolute recurrence rates observed, the cumulative proportion of patients who ultimately require ALND after an omission strategy remains small.[40,42]

When event rates are extremely low and follow-up remains limited, statistical exactness is inherently constrained. Wide confidence intervals and low subgroup event counts increase the risk of Type II error, particularly in biologically aggressive or underrepresented subgroups. Extended follow-up from the INSEMA trial and publication of mature oncologic data from the BOOG 2013-08 study will be essential to confirm the long-term durability of omission strategies.[11,40,42]

Interim Interpretation:

The SOUND and INSEMA trials provide statistically significant evidence that SLNB omission is not inferior within predefined margins for early- and intermediate-term outcomes in carefully selected clinically node-negative patients undergoing breast-conserving therapy. However, the short follow-up duration, low event rates, and limited power in specific biological subgroups warrant cautious long-term interpretation. Future studies with extended follow-up and greater representation of underrepresented subgroups are necessary to determine the durability and greater applicability of these outcomes. Therefore, SLNB omission should be regarded as evidence-supported within the studied populations rather than as proof of absolute or lifelong oncologic equivalence.

Conformance with International Consensus Recommendations

The findings from the SOUND and INSEMA trials, along with emerging evidence from BOOG 2013-08, are largely consistent with the latest recommendations of the St. Gallen International Consensus Conference. The consensus panel cautiously endorsed omitting sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) in a narrowly defined patient group: postmenopausal women with stage I breast cancer, hormone receptor-positive and HER2-negative tumours, and negative axillary ultrasound, provided that pathological nodal information would not notably influence adjuvant therapy decisions.[43]

Conversely, the panel recommended maintaining SLNB in several clinical scenarios, including premenopausal patients, individuals with larger tumours or high histological grade, and those with HER2-positive or triple-negative disease. These reservations parallel the omission trials, in which higher-risk biological subgroups were underrepresented and not independently validated for non-inferiority.[43]

A significant proportion of the panel also opposed the routine omission of SLNB in patients with invasive lobular carcinoma (ILC). This stance was based on concerns about the diagnostic performance of axillary ultrasound in this histological subtype and the limited inclusion of ILC in randomised omission studies.[44]

Diagnostic difficulties associated with ILC have been well documented. The discohesive growth pattern of lobular carcinoma often results in diffuse cortical infiltration within lymph nodes, unlike the focal enlargement typically seen in invasive

ductal carcinoma (IDC). Consequently, axillary metastases from ILC may produce only subtle imaging changes. Retrospective analyses indicate that axillary ultrasound is less sensitive for detecting metastatic nodes in ILC than in IDC, with identification rates of approximately 35–55% for ILC and 60–75% for IDC. Correspondingly, false-negative rates are higher in lobular tumours. This may be due to ILC metastases causing less pronounced cortical thickening and fewer clear morphological changes on ultrasound.[45]

Given these restrictions in imaging sensitivity and the lack of randomised trials specifically validating omission in this subgroup, the routine avoidance of SLNB in ILC cannot currently be considered evidence equivalent to its omission in IDC.

The patient populations in SOUND and INSEMA closely correspond to those identified by the St. Gallen panel as suitable candidates for omission. In both trials, most patients had small tumours, predominantly HR+/HER2– profiles, negative standardised axillary ultrasound, and received breast-conserving surgery followed by radiotherapy. Within these defined parameters, omission of SLNB did not compromise short- to intermediate-term oncologic outcomes. However, neither current consensus recommendations nor available randomised data support extending omission strategies exceeding these parameters. Evidence continues to be insufficient for patients with initially node-positive disease, inflammatory breast cancer, biologically aggressive tumour subtypes, or clinical scenarios in which nodal staging is critical for systemic therapy or radiotherapy planning.

In this context, contemporary randomised evidence should not be interpreted as superseding expert consensus. Instead, these trials provide prospective support for a carefully selected axillary de-escalation strategy based on biological risk stratification, high-quality axillary imaging, and individualised multidisciplinary decision-making.

Proposed Clinical Selection Algorithm

This pragmatic framework is primarily based on eligibility criteria and oncologic outcomes reported in the fully published randomised phase III trials SOUND and INSEMA. Elements of the algorithm are further informed by emerging data from the BOOG 2013-08 trial; however, as mature peer-reviewed results from BOOG remain limited, these aspects should be regarded as provisional and subject to confirmation with longer follow-up.[11-13] For visual comprehension, Figure 1 provides a summary flowchart of the proposed patient selection algorithm, showing key decision points and criteria for consideration of SLNB omission based on the aggregated trial evidence.

This scheme aims to support a structured multidisciplinary evaluation. However, this does not represent a formal guideline or directive for standard clinical practice. The strength of the supporting evidence is stratified by clinical context.

Step 1: Clinical Eligibility

Strongest Evidence (Direct Randomised Validation) The omission of SLNB may be considered in patients who fulfil all of the following criteria:

- cT1 invasive breast cancer (≤ 2 cm)
- Clinically node-negative (cN0) axilla on physical examination
- Planned breast-conserving surgery

- Planned whole-breast irradiation delivered using conventional tangential fields, or a radiotherapy technique that ensures incidental coverage of level I-II axillary nodes

This clinical profile closely corresponds to that of the SOUND trial, which used a conservative non-inferiority margin and a systemic endpoint.[1,11,12,39]

Limited or Preliminary Evidence

- **cT2 tumours (2–5 cm)** Although patients with cT2 disease were included in INSEMA and BOOG 2013-08, these trials did not establish subgroup-specific non-inferiority for this category. Therefore, the omission of SLNB in cT2 tumours remains investigational until mature, peer-reviewed subgroup analyses are available.[1,13,39]

Absolute Indication for SLNB

Presence of any clinically suspicious axillary lymph node The strength of the recommendation depends on the tumour size and biological characteristics. Current evidence does not support the universal omission of SLNB in all clinically node-negative patients.[46,47]

Step 2: Axillary Imaging

In many omission trials, particularly SOUND and BOOG 2013-08, patient selection relied on standardised preoperative axillary ultrasound to exclude clinically occult nodal disease. Within the framework proposed in this review, the use of quality-controlled axillary ultrasound is therefore considered a pragmatic and conservative strategy to support safe patient selection when SLNB is omitted. To be considered compatible with omission, the ultrasound evaluation should demonstrate the following: [42, 48, 49]

- Cortical thickness within accepted normal limits (commonly ≤ 2.5 -3mm). For example, the BOOG 2013-08 protocol used a threshold of >2.3 mm to trigger needle biopsy of suspicious lymph nodes. This value reflects a protocol-specific imaging rule rather than a universally established diagnostic cutoff and is presented here for contextual reference.
- Preserved fatty hilum
- Absence of focal cortical bulging or eccentric cortical hypertrophy
- No rounded nodal morphology
- No abnormal peripheral vascularisation

Any suspicious lymph nodes identified during imaging should undergo tissue sampling using fine-needle aspiration (FNA) or core needle biopsy.[50] If the imaging results are indeterminate, technically suboptimal, or unavailable, SLNB should be performed. Ultrasound assessment should be performed by dedicated breast radiologists using high-quality linear transducers. Institutional quality assurance mechanisms are key for assuring consistent imaging performance.[48,49] Because the omission trials enrolled imaging-selected populations, the reproducibility of high-quality axillary ultrasound is a key factor in external validity.

Step 3: Tumour Biology and Subgroup Considerations

Population with Evidence-Based Validation

The most robust randomised evidence pertains to patients with the following tumour characteristics: [39,51]

- Hormone receptor-positive disease
- HER2-negative status
- Low to intermediate histological grade (Grade 1–2) is most strongly represented in the randomised trial populations. Although grade 3 tumours were included in SOUND and INSEMA, the number of such cases was relatively limited, and subgroup-specific analyses lacked sufficient statistical power to establish non-inferiority with the same level of confidence.
- Tumor size ≤ 2 cm

Subgroups Lacking Independent Validation

Several clinically significant subgroups were underrepresented in omission trials and consequently lacked dedicated non-inferiority validation:[32,39,51]

- Triple-negative breast cancer
- HER2-positive tumors
- Grade3 tumours
- Invasive lobular carcinoma (ILC)
- cT2 tumors

Menopausal Status as a Clinical Consideration

Premenopausal women were included in the omission trials; however, these studies were not intended to provide subgroup-specific conclusions for this population.[24] In younger patients, the nodal status more frequently informs key therapeutic decisions, including.

- Indication for chemotherapy
- Selection of ovarian suppression strategies
- Consideration of regional nodal irradiation

Therefore, the omission of SLNB in premenopausal patients should be handled with care and requires an individualised multidisciplinary evaluation. Chronological age alone is not an absolute exclusion criterion. However, clinical reliance on nodal information is generally greater in younger individuals.[29]

Step 4: Multidisciplinary Team Confirmation

Prior to the omission of the SLNB, the multidisciplinary team should confirm the following conditions:

- Systemic therapy recommendations are unlikely to be materially altered by pathological nodal information. [24,39]
- The radiotherapy plan should be reviewed to ensure that the dose distribution approximates the incidental axillary exposure generally achieved with conventional tangential whole-breast irradiation. Dosimetric evaluation should confirm that level I axillary nodes receive a clinically meaningful portion of the prescribed breast dose, typically corresponding to a mean dose of approximately 60–70% of the prescription dose with partial high-dose exposure (e.g., measurable V90–95%), while assuring that the lower axilla is not completely excluded when highly conformal techniques such as IMRT or VMAT are used.[13, 36, 52]

- Decisions regarding neoadjuvant therapy are not dependent on nodal staging.[53]
- Reliable oncologic follow-up may be maintained.[10]

Shared decision-making with the patient is essential. Discussions should clearly communicate that current evidence demonstrates statistical non-inferiority rather than strict equivalence and that long-term follow-up remains limited. Patients should be informed about the potential benefits of avoiding surgical morbidity as well as the small but uncertain risk of occult nodal disease or future regional recurrence. Treatment decisions should therefore incorporate patient preferences regarding acceptable levels of uncertainty and risk within the context of multidisciplinary clinical recommendations.

Eliciting the patient's opinions and preferences on acceptable uncertainty can enrich collaborative, individualised decision-making.[24,39]

Contraindications to SLNB Omission

Sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) is indicated in the following clinical scenarios:[39,46, 53]

- Clinically suspicious axillary lymph nodes
- Inadequate or non-standardised axial imaging
- Planned mastectomy
- Inflammatory breast cancer
- Extensive multifocal disease (>2 separate quadrants or >5 cm aggregate span)
- Clinical situations in which nodal status is presumed to influence adjuvant or neoadjuvant treatment decisions

Implementation Caveats

Implementation of SLNB omission strategies needs close scrutiny of the radiotherapy technique.

- Randomised omission trials were conducted predominantly using conventional tangential whole-breast irradiation, which delivered a consistent dose to level I and portions of level II axillary nodes [39,52].
- In contemporary practice, highly conformal modalities (IMRT, VMAT, and proton therapy) may substantially reduce axillary exposure unless coverage is intentionally evaluated during the planning phase [53].
- When SLNB is omitted, reliance on incidental, unverified radiation doses to the axilla is insufficient. Dosimetric assessment should confirm adequate lower axillary coverage consistent with the radiobiological context of randomised trials [53].
- Institutions adopting omission strategies should ensure that radiotherapy planning protocols are aligned with the technical assumptions underlying the trial evidence [39,54].

Conceptual Summary

Based on the current evidence, the omission of sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) should be interpreted as follows:

- Evidence-supported strategy for rigorously selected patients with cT1, hormone receptor-positive/HER2-negative tumors, demonstrating non-inferiority with respect to early- and intermediate-term regional and distant recurrence. Long-term safety beyond the current follow-up horizon, notably regarding late distant metastasis in HR-positive disease, remains to be confirmed[24,39]

Pragmatic Clinical Decision Framework for Consideration of Sentinel Lymph Node Biopsy (SLNB) Omission in Early-Stage cN0 Breast Cancer

Derived from randomized phase III trials: SOUND, INSEMA, BOOG 2013-08. Not prospectively validated as a guideline.

Figure 1 Pragmatic clinical decision-making framework for consideration of sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) omission in early-stage clinically node-negative (cN0) breast cancer.

- A hypothesis-generating approach for cT2 tumours and biologically aggressive subtypes[32,39]
- Dependent on the availability of high-quality imaging and appropriate radiotherapy techniques[52]
- A selective method of surgical de-escalation rather than a universal change to standard clinical practice[24,47]

Context of Clinical Guidelines

Current international consensus guidelines recommend a careful approach to omitting sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB), supporting this practice primarily for a narrowly defined subset of older patients (aged ≥ 70 years) with small, hormone receptor-positive, HER2-negative tumours, in whom pathological nodal status is unlikely to influence adjuvant therapy decisions. These guidelines specify essential prerequisites for safe implementation, including standardised preoperative axillary ultrasound, formal multidisciplinary case review, and comprehensive systems for long-term oncologic surveillance.[39]

These recommendations apply to a narrowly defined patient population characterised by favourable tumour biology and limited anticipated reliance on nodal status for therapy. They should not be construed as a general endorsement of axillary de-escalation in all clinically node-negative patients.[39,55]

Figure 1 presents a pragmatic clinical decision-making framework for appraising the omission of sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) in patients with clinically node-negative (cN0) early-stage invasive breast cancer undergoing breast-conserving surgery. This system is based on eligibility criteria and oncologic safety outcomes from the SOUND, INSEMA, and BOOG 2013-08 randomised trials. The omission of SLNB may be considered for patients with cT1 tumours (≤ 2 cm), favourable biological

features, and negative, quality-assured preoperative axillary ultrasound findings, particularly when axillary status is unlikely to affect systemic therapy or regional radiotherapy. The inclusion of cT2 tumours warrants caution. SLNB remains indicated for patients with clinically suspicious lymph nodes, inadequate imaging, planned mastectomy, inflammatory breast cancer, or subgroups with aggressive tumour biology or insufficient validation.

This proposed algorithm accentuates the importance of multidisciplinary evaluation and joint decision-making. It has not been prospectively validated and should not be regarded as a formal clinical guideline or standard-of-care recommendation.

Why SLNB Is Not Yet Obsolete

Population-based data highlight the continued clinical relevance of sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB). If SLNB were universally omitted in patients with cT1N0, hormone receptor-positive/HER2-negative breast cancer, approximately 11%–20% would still present with pathological nodal metastases [24,47]. Introducing this numeric range underscores that even within this favourable group, a meaningful proportion harbours occult node-positive disease. For certain subgroups, particularly younger or premenopausal patients, determining nodal status remains important for guiding therapeutic decisions, including the demand for chemotherapy, the choice of ovarian suppression, and the consideration of regional nodal irradiation.[24,39]

The objective of current axillary management is to optimise, rather than eliminate, nodal staging by identifying patients for whom staging information is unlikely to affect treatment decisions, while preserving it for those in whom it remains clinically relevant. In this context, SLNB continues to yield actionable

pathological data for selected patients. Contemporary axillary management prioritises careful patient selection based on tumour biology, imaging accuracy, and the expected influence of nodal findings on treatment planning.[24,47]

Cost-Benefit and Resource Considerations

In addition to oncologic safety, the financial consequences of SLNB omission warrant consideration. Sentinel lymph node biopsy requires operating room time, nuclear medicine resources, pathological assessment, and potential management of surgical complications. Therefore, omission of SLNB may reduce direct procedural costs and downstream morbidity-related expenditures.[33,56]

However, omission strategies rely on standardised, high-quality axillary ultrasound performed by experienced radiologists, often with image-guided needle biopsy of suspicious nodes. Such imaging-based selection introduces its own resource utilisation and may partially offset surgical cost savings. The economic balance between surgical omission and intensified imaging strategies has not yet been fully quantified in mature peer-reviewed analyses.[33]

The BOOG 2013-08 trial included cost-effectiveness as a pre-defined secondary endpoint, and its final analyses are expected to provide more definitive data on healthcare resource utilisation.[13] Until comprehensive economic evaluations become available, the omission of SLNB should be interpreted mainly through an oncologic safety lens rather than presumed cost reduction.

Conclusion

Recent randomised trials (SOUND, INSEMA) and emerging phase III data from BOOG 2013-08 demonstrate that the omission of sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) is statistically non-inferior to standard axillary staging for early- and intermediate-term outcomes in carefully selected patients with early-stage, clinically node-negative breast cancer undergoing breast-conserving therapy. These findings correspond with current international consensus recommendations, as exemplified by those from the St. Gallen International Breast Cancer Conference, which support SLNB omission primarily in narrowly defined populations characterized by favorable tumor biology, negative axillary imaging, and limited impact of nodal status on adjuvant treatment decisions. In this context, the translation of omission strategies into clinical practice should be guided by strict adherence to evidence-based selection criteria and multidisciplinary evaluation, making certain that SLNB omission is applied only to patients meeting established trial parameters and guideline-supported indications.

These data apply primarily to biologically favourable populations characterised by small tumours, predominant hormone receptor-positive/HER2-negative disease, negative quality-assured axillary ultrasound, and receipt of whole-breast irradiation. They do not support the indiscriminate discontinuation of axillary staging.

Interpretation requires caution. Non-inferiority was established within predefined statistical margins; however, confidence intervals remained relatively wide due to low event rates and subgroup-specific analyses being underpowered. Moreover, given the predominance of hormone receptor-positive tumours, long-term safety—notably concerning late distant recurrence beyond 10 years—remains to be confirmed.

Therefore, SLNB is not obsolete but has been selectively repositioned within a biologically informed treatment paradigm. Omission may be considered when the pre-test probability of clinically meaningful nodal involvement is sufficiently low, and treatment recommendations are unlikely to change irrespective of pathological nodal findings.

Future priorities include extended long-term follow-up, validation in biologically aggressive subtypes (e.g., triple-negative and HER2-positive disease), and evaluation in the neoadjuvant setting. Several major ongoing and upcoming trials, such as NAUTILUS and EUBREAST-01, are actively evaluating the safety of omitting SLNB in diverse clinical settings, including imaging-based patient selection and post-neoadjuvant therapy scenarios. The results of these studies will deliver vital data that may enhance or expand the applicability of omission strategies in the coming years. Until such data mature, SLNB omission should remain a selective, context-dependent de-escalation strategy rather than a universal standard of care.

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The clinical algorithm illustrated in Figure 1 was developed by the authors; the graphical layout was prepared using AI-assisted design tools.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that no conflicts of interest for this study.

Ethics committee approval:

Ethical approval was not required for this study because it is a review article based exclusively on previously published data and does not involve human participants, patient data, or animal subjects.

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